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Catch-EyoU has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement (G.A n. 649538; 2015-2018).

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2018 Forum Nazionale dei Giovani

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INTRODUCTION

Before diving ourselves in this Toolkit containing success stories of participation promoted by various European youth organizations, it is necessary to introduce some of the motivations that have pushed the editors to produce a document that hopefully will become a reference point for all those youth workers and stakeholders who are involved in implementing and organizing activities for young Europeans and their active citizenship.

The “Catch EyoU Toolkit - practices of active participation” is one of the outcomes expected from the project “Catch EyoU - Constructing Active Citizenship with European Youth: Policies, Practices, Challenges and Solution” funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 649538 and coordinated by the Department of Psychology, Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna together with Örebro University (SE), Friedrich Schiller University University Jena (DE), National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (GR), University of Porto (PT), Masaryk University (CZ), the London Schools of Economics and Political Science (UK), University of Tartu (EE) and Forum Nazionale dei Giovani (IT). The latter, the only partner not from the academic sector, is the Italian youth council and responsible for this publication (with a related electronic version) to be distributed to youth organizations, youth workers and stakeholders with the aim of improving their ability to promote the participation of young people and the active citizenship across positive actions at national or local level.

Through the joint contribution of different disciplines (Psychology, Political Science, Sociology, Media and Communications, Education) the three-year “Catch EyoU” project had the aim to identify the factors, located at different levels (psychological, developmental, macro social and contextual) influencing the different forms of youth active engagement in Europe. Through different work packages and studies, qualitative (WP3, WP5, WP6, WP8), quantitative (WP4, WP7), and an active citizenship intervention in schools (WP9), the project provided a multifaceted understanding of the different factors influencing the perspectives of young people on Europe and of the ways in which young people engage in society, offering policy makers new instruments and "conceptual lenses" to better understand this generation, how they approach public authorities and how they engage materially and symbolically in order to participate in the construction of the societies they inhabit and shape the governmental regimes under which they live.

This Toolkit was created thanks to the contribution of the Coordinator of the International Youth Panel of the project and two Experts from the “Pool of Trainers” of Forum Nazionale Giovani. The result to be achieved is to translate in a simple and suitable way, the cross-sectorial ethnography analyse on European success cases contained within the Deliverable 8.2 titled “Contexts, meanings and successful practices of young people’s participation: a cross-national report”.

In our time, full of new challenges for our society and for young people, the aim is to allow all European youth organizations, youth workers and stakeholders to understand and exploit the results of the project in a practical and long-term perspective.

Maria Cristina Pisani – Spokesperson Fng
Giulio Raimondo – Board Member Fng

PRESENTATION OF THE TOOLKIT

The term “Toolkit” generally applies to a container of tools for building something that are kept “in one place.” The arrangement allows the person using the box to quickly find and use tools in order to “build or fix” more efficiently.

The idea behind this publication is exactly that: a container of successful stories of participation in order to inspire young people, youth organisations and stakeholders in promoting and supporting active European citizenship.

Participation takes many forms, a person can participate and be an active citizenship not only by voting or by belonging to a political party, it's possible to be an active citizenship by acting to change something that it considered not equal. Education can be part of active citizenship, as well as sharing and multiplying its own personal experiences to their peers.

The ethnographic researches carried on in 8 European countries by the project “Catch EyoU - Constructing Active Citizenship with European Youth: Policies, Practices, Challenges and Solution” have underlined the multiple and creative forms of active citizenship among young Europeans.

The methodology of the ethnographic research allowed the researchers to go deeper in some details thanks to interviews and field visits carried on within 8 months. They collected pages and pages of information, insights and points of view that are here collected and condensate. The project also provided recommendations on how to promote and support active citizenship towards different stakeholders. Two kind of recommendations were produced: some directly born from the researches and others developed by an international youth panel composed by european youngsters and experts active in the field.

To bring all these experiences in "one place" and to describe them in an accessible and ready-to-use way were the objectives of the following Toolkit. It addresses youth organisations, youth workers and stakeholders dealing with participation, active citizenship and European citizenship, its aim is to inspire them with successful stories and to give the possibility to replicate them.

The information are organized within categories and for each of these categories sub categories have been identified: this division will provide targeted direction to the specific needs of the reader, making accessible and ready to use activities and best practices. The recommendations conclude each category by underlining the steps to do in order to support particular aspects of active participation among young people.

As a result from the project research and following the main packages field, four main categories have been identified:

- Involving young people in policy dialogue (related to WP3)
- Active European citizenship for all (related to WP4)
- Raising the youth voice within old and new media (related to WP5)
- Formal and non formal educational context (related to WP6)

Each successful story is described by a synthetic form that will help understand the practice and the environment in which the practice is developed.

Thanks to the synthetic form it will be possible to know the genesis of the organisation (with its aims and objectives), the main implemented activities and how they are implemented. In order to go deeper to the practices a section with features and challenges will help the reader to take into account the key for success and the risks. A final section reports thoughts and comments of the young people involved in the practice, giving an insight of the feelings and the motivation of the protagonists.

The conclusions will describe the final comments and recommendations on the whole WP8 deliverable, titled “Contexts, meanings and successful practices of young people’s participation: a cross-national report” and addressed for youth civic organizations and stakeholders.

We hope you could get the most from this Toolkit and be inspired by these successful stories of engagement and participation.

INVOLVING YOUNG PEOPLE IN POLICY DIALOGUE

CONSTRUCTING DEMOCRACY

BEING A SOCIAL CHANGE MAKER

PLATFORM OF YOUTH ORGANIZATIONS

EUROPEAN STRUCTURED DIALOGUE

RECOMMENDATIONS

CONSTRUCTING DEMOCRACY

- **MOMENTUM**
- **IDEALISTE**
- **SCOUT CENTRE “THIRTEEN”**

CONSTRUCTING DEMOCRACY MOMENTUM

WWW.PEOPLESMOMENTUM.COM

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Join a political movement
Support your political movement

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Momentum, focused explicitly on campaigning to popularise, modify and support the politics, policies and election of Labour party leader Jeremy Corbyn. Momentum is an incredible and almost accidental success story in active citizenship.

It is a cross-generational progressive leftwing activist organisation and political campaign group. It supports current socialist Labour party policies and the leader of the Labour opposition Jeremy Corbyn. Momentum was founded in September 2015 by four Labour Party activists from different backgrounds.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

Try to get people to the polls to vote for their favoured candidate.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

They organise and invite Momentum members and supporters in particular marginal constituencies to attend local training and canvassing events. These are conducted quite theatrically and pedagogically in partnership with American activists from the Bernie Sanders campaign, who shared techniques on ‘persuasive door knocking,’ which proved to be an engaging and unthreatening way of training first time activists, while innovating on traditional canvassing approaches.

See also in this toolkit:

Category *RAISING THE YOUTH VOICE WITHIN OLD AND NEW MEDIA*
Sub category *FROM ONLINE-TO-OFFLINE TO SOCIAL MEDIA VIRALITY (MOMENTUM)*

○ FEATURES:

The organisational system of structural democracy and horizontal management. Trust in their even newest members and reflexive self starting and self completing activism

Fun and friendly atmosphere both in the office and in the events they organise - being "youthful".

Strong sense of self-awareness regarding the need to make politics do able and interesting for people

○ CHALLENGES:

To find right methodology for trainings and keep up the motivation of the volunteers
Lack of socioeconomic diversity within the volunteer pool (being a volunteer means to dedicate free time to the activity)
Risk of misrepresentation by the official media because of non conventional approaches used

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

The people are a really important part of keeping people engaged. Why Momentum and Take Back Control and The World Transformed is special is because, we're trying to make politics, like, fun [laughs]. And also, inclusive and diverse. And, that makes you want to stay, because it's somewhere that you're happy to be with good people who are doing good things. I think for lots of people—especially who get involved in the Labour Party—drop out quite quickly, because it's not a nice atmosphere. It's, like... there's a lot of hostility. It's very... old, very male, very white. It's very boring [laughs]. And so even if you think you're doing good work, there's not... there's no spark. Brenda, 20

There are two male presenters and one female. They seem in their 30s. They are very upbeat, very animated. There is a clear attempt to lift and energise people. A large container of chewy sweets is passed around and this gesture is received well by people. I am an experienced political activist, and it is unlike any political meeting I have been to. There is a big element of performance on the part of the hosts. It's almost as if the organisers (the people wearing Momentum T-shirts) are trying to model and convey political energy; they seem to be conscious of the need to engage at all times. It's as if they want the people in attendance, young and old, to want to come back. Field Notes, Momentum National Conference, 25 March 2017, Birmingham

CONSTRUCTING DEMOCRACY IDEALISTE

WWW.IDEALISTE.CZ

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Youth as a topic and as a target group

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Idealiste is a registered “progressivist and culturally liberal” civic and political association focused on political issues.

The Idealists are successful in attracting youth on social networking sites, and on Facebook especially; its chairman Radim Hejduk became the most popular candidate on Facebook, with more fans than the prime minister Sobotka, with very positive contents and successful projects on his and the Idealists page. It started from a core of 20 young friends and became a success story of young people more in support of democracy, interested in politics, with a higher political efficacy and more tolerant with a higher social trust in comparison to the general population of Czech Youth (20-26 years old). They also record lower alienation from political institutions and much lower authoritarianism.

“We are building our association on freedom, justice and solidarity”

They are equipped with a broad repertoire of participation, focused on the national politics but not making borderline between national and supranational (European) level.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

Involving young people for different purposes: the Idealists are a political organisation, so mostly focused on political issues.

○ **HOW THEY DO IT:**

Top-Down communication in the association.

Horizontal communication among members.

Horizontal communication toward new members and people interested in membership.

○ **FEATURES:**

The organisation has clear hierarchy and well-developed democracy, many of their activities are based on informal rules, relationships, everyday meetings (or communication) of few people, routines and friendships that also works as long-term motivations.

So, key powers keeping the key members engaged despite of long-term over-load are the informal relationships in the association.

○ CHALLENGES:

The Idealists are part of the establishment and they want to be although the main idea of the Idealists and its position in system is challenged and questioned by many association members, as well as connection to several institutions.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

We've gradually been setting up a group for the young from 15 to up to 21 or 25. There are just a few of us, maybe 6, and some of the boys are brilliant. For example, XX, that's a really smart kid. He's just been to the World Debating Championship, which is a similar group like the summit one, and he is ambitious and really good. So, it's super to have someone like him in the Idealists. We were thinking we could set up something in the same format and visit grammar schools to address young people. That's one of the challenges, because I think we do address people through the media, but personal contact is useful because you can ask them to fill in the registration form or tell them to come to a meeting or an event. (The Idealists, omissis, male)

CONSTRUCTING DEMOCRACY

SCOUT CENTRE “THIRTEEN”

WWW.TRINACTKA.COM

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Attracting youth and let them decide together

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

“Thirteen” is a Scout centre, led by young people and with a well-developed democracy working approach.

Their idea of active citizenship can be seen in their values and agency as well as in education of children and younger scouts; they also perceived that the idea of citizenship is contained in the laws of Scouts (to be Scout=to be active citizen).

Active citizenship stems mostly from “caring” about surroundings, people, environment or the whole community. It is very focused on the broader community and on civic acts embedded in every-day life, not on institutional politics. This is for them about everydayness, about values, self-development (with focus on soft skills) and responsibility. Although the Scouts is perceived as non-partisan, according to respondent it cannot be strictly apolitical because of its values (which aims to raise active citizenship).

WHAT THEY DO:

The activity of “Thirteen” is focused more on leisure time education of young people and on development of civic values than on specific political activities.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

Negotiations and differences among members (“it depends on people”).

Strong focus on communication, related to exchange of experiences and feedback.

○ FEATURES:

Activities of organisation are not paid, they are based on volunteering and have clear hierarchy and well-developed democracy; many of their activities are based on informal rules, relationships, everyday meetings (or communication) of few people, routines and friendships that also works as long-term motivations.

So, key powers are the informal relationships in the associations, solidarity, responsibility and friendships.

○ CHALLENGES:

The structure of the centre is decentralised (several troops), the main challenge is to maintain the level of communication between them and the link with the other groups and institutions, also because they are dependent on membership fees (and donations).

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

We talked about that your centre is quite specific. Why?

It's only my opinion, but it comes from the past events, and that, under their weight, we had to stick together and work as one group, because there was a decline in the number of children and there weren't many leaders either, and those who stayed were not many and they were quite young. They took it over and shared experiences, or tried to, and it's now growing thanks to the generation that's growing up. ("The Thirteen", Mayor, male)

BEING A SOCIAL CHANGE MAKER

● **CIDADE+**

● **GREENPEACE JUGEND**

BEING A SOCIAL CHANGE MAKER

CIDADE+

WWW.CIDADEMAIS.PT

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Link and discuss ecology and politics
Create a multilevel network around a topic
Professionalize your activities

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Cidade+ is an informal group, integrated in a formal association “Moving Cause”, located in the city of Porto. The idea behind Cidade+ is to raise environmental awareness, reflected on day-to-day actions from home to the way we all relate with each other and make business trades; to promote a network of civic, economic and political actors concerned with environmental action/ social responsibility; and to make an effective change on politics, in Portugal and amongst its citizens. The founders, already active in the field, decided to start a group in order to create professionally-minded commitment and input towards the project, as they wanted to create something relevant and effective. They applied for different entrepreneurship programme which enabled them to start working full time, since March 2013, with a group of three people. Since then, they have been managing different funding aiming the financial sustainability of the project.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

The main activity is a public 4-days’ event focusing on environment and sustainability in a big local garden in Porto. This event is preceded by a “warm-up cycle” (3-months of events until the final weekend), trying to ‘create community’. This event entails conferences and debates to reflect on ideas, from institutional to academy or common citizen’ audiences. “Business plazas” – for companies which work for sustainability to be close and get to know each other and regular citizens. “Mercadeco” [little marketplace] – a space for trade and to present on-growing projects related to handicraft, food, clothing, with an area for associations. Workshops - to schools, families or adults - with various dimensions from physical health to recycling tools. Shows – music, performances, and dance – to celebrate sustainability and the environment with a positive attitude.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

To set up the main event, the group organised smaller activities (the warm-up cycle) , throughout the year, in which they usually worked with small groups, grounded on co-creation, and equipped with participatory tools and methodologies to foster everyone's participation. They did use the ideas and materials raised from the event's production. This co-creation process is extended to the network they hold, providing space, time and voice, for citizens, enterprises, political institutions and academics.

The event is supported by the local municipality of Porto with a formal partnership which includes the inclusion of the group's activities in the Municipality agenda, availability of spaces and human resources, plus a public funding. The co-financing of the event is also one of their strategies in order to be efficient and promote a direct implication from partners, moreover they use crowd-funding as a form of public selection and commitment.

At the end of the event the activists always plan dissemination activities, considering their impact on public visibility, so they implement a professional use of political marketing and media.

○ FEATURES:

The social capital of each member of the group as well as the social capital from the entire group have an important impact on the upbringings of the group and on the political and civic participation of its members. The group is enlarged by formal and informal partnerships: they hold a "friendship network" that involves different agents, activists and civil society.

The ability to place itself in-between the institutional sphere and the public realm. The professionally-minded commitment. The members tend to pursue a horizontal decision-making process, perceiving their internal structure as a shared-leadership.

Volunteer work used by the group both to meet the needs of the event' production and as an opportunity to engage others in the movement journey.

○ CHALLENGES:

The professionalization process reveal some limits and tensions related to: bu-
reaucratization; institutional presence that can entail risks of co-optation or de-
viance from the main goals; accuracy of communication and formalisation of
speech, that has to change depending to which partner you are dealing with;
running for funding is a constant matter so the members experience a preca-
riousness.

Constantly need of impact measurement in order to get financing.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

Many problems in society that begin with the young people who are going to be tomorrow's adults,
is that they don't have that good challenge or that motivation let's say, that feeling of being alive.
Because in fact, they don't feel alive because they're not co-creating! Co-creating is the unknown.
[...]The surprise is lost. The contribution that someone can give that has never been seen before, is
lost. (Henrique)

With regard to *Cidade+*, I see community as people who gets hold of the event. And for that I have
to give up of any idea of possession that I might have from the event...[...]Community is not stupid!
(Laughter) other people aren't stupid! (Laughter) that is something one can feel! And for the people...
they have to feel that what they bring is valued, is listened and has an impact in the same measurement
has they are willing to give. So I see that community... I really see *Cidade+* being organised by a
community that gathers people and projects and that meets up regularly to define... (Viviana)

BEING A SOCIAL CHANGE MAKER

GREENPEACE JUGEND

WWW.GREENPEACE-JUGEND.DE

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Join an environmental organisation
Use innovative and creative practice

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Greenpeace is an international environmental organisation that operates by way of direct nonviolent actions to draw attention to the protection of nature and justice for all living creatures. Greenpeace was founded in 1971 in Vancouver, Canada. Greenpeace Germany was established nine years later, in 1980, so it can be considered to be a fairly long standing organisation, nationally. Greenpeace Jugend is a subgroup of Greenpeace Germany founded in 2014, which itself is a subgroup of International Greenpeace, and focuses on both younger children up to age 14 and youth up to 18 years.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

In general Greenpeace acts on four different levels (local, regional, national and international). They work on topics such as energy, climate and climate change, biodiversity (forest, seas) and agriculture (genetic engineering / pesticides) and, if possible, all other current topics.

Greenpeace considers active citizenship through face-to-face non-violent direct actions, information, exhibitions, lectures, flyers to inform people about current political shortcomings in dealing with environmental issues.

Additional to the aims and main activities given by Greenpeace Germany and Greenpeace international, the local group formulate the goals of recruiting new members as well as planning new actions to gain as much as possible attention by people in the city.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

The group is organised via grassroots democracy by their members and members are all equal. An exception is made for one member who takes responsibility for the key of the meeting room and also received further information from the national Greenpeace group. They also have connections to the Greenpeace group which is organised by grownups in the same city, with members starting from age 18. Once a month they have a joint meeting of both groups. Sometimes members of the adult group join Greenpeace Jugend meetings, for supporting them, especially for realising actions.

Greenpeace Germany offers commuting young members to refund the transport tickets, for weekly meetings or for camps in other parts of Germany. By giving this opportunity, Greenpeace diminishes problems resulting in staying away from the group for economic reasons and encourages the youth to join the meetings.

○ FEATURES:

Members of the Greenpeace Jugend knew, from a theoretical angle, both how active citizenship is functioning in a democracy and how to transform it into a practical action. They paid particular attention on the well-being of each member and they all described each other as equal and they have a code of conduct they can follow about being environmentally friendly and they also put across these attitudes to other people by informing and reminding other people of this code of conduct

○ CHALLENGES:

The workload in organising events/protest can be unequally distributed.

Lack of support and guidance by older and more experienced members.

Behaving in an environmentally friendly way implies on the one hand spending more money and on the other hand the risk of being stigmatized as "greenies".

No feedback reported after the event they organised.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

So that we are more young people, so that they are able to change something and so they aren't so ignorant and keep on throwing their plastic waste everywhere. That they gain a view for the important topics.

On one hand it is a nice way to meet friends, and people with similar views, concerning the environment as well as having a deeper exchange and communication than just partying. And one can do events. I nearly always find it great to publicly show up interesting facts. Precisely in the youth group there are a lot of possibilities to use creative methods. (Interview to one member)

You somehow hear of global warming, what it is and what exactly is going wrong. And there are things that happen, like when one person alone takes a big car to work in the morning. It is just completely unnecessary. It doesn't give you an advantage, instead you are too lazy and destroy the environment. It makes me contemplate and I just want to do something against it, even if it isn't easy to achieve. (Interview to one member)

- **FORUM NAZIONALE DEI GIOVANI - FNG**
- **EUROPEAN YOUTH FORUM**

PLATFORM OF YOUTH ORGANISATION

FORUM NAZIONALE DEI GIOVANI - FNG

WWW.FORUMNAZIONALEGIOVANI.IT

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Create a National platform of youth organisation
Be active at national level in a network of youth organisation dealing with advocacy and lobbying in youth policy
Support the implementation of youth policy in your country

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

The Italian National Youth Forum (FNG), recognized by the Legislative Decree of Italian Parliament n. 311 of 30 December 2004, is the only National Platform of Italian Youth organizations.

It counts currently 75 member organizations and it acknowledges a delegation of more than 4 million young people.

The Forum strength relies in the variety of its member organizations, which reflects the heterogeneous modalities of youth commitment.

The Italian National Youth Forum is member of the European Youth Forum (YFJ) which represents the interests of the European Youth in the major international institutions.

WHAT THEY DO:

The purpose of the Italian Youth Forum is to involve young people in the social and political debate creating opportunity of active citizenship, youth participation and European awareness.

It is committed to promote the concept of youth policy as an integrated and cross-sectoral element of overall policy development.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

The Italian Youth Forum aims at:

Creating opportunities of meeting, debating and sharing of experiences between member organisations and Institutions.

Facilitating cooperation and networking between member organisations.

Promoting the creation of Youth Forums and Youth Councils at a local and regional level.

The Executive Board is composed of 9 persons elected by the Congress. They are responsible for the implementation of the work plan and the development of the Italian Youth Forum. Board members are elected for three-year terms. The General Assembly is the highest decision making body of the Forum. It shall meet at least twice a year. Each member organisation has the right to vote. Every three years the Congress elects the Speaker and the Board and defines the policies of the Forum for the following two years.

Its work is also made by the thematic commissions, namely:

- Foreign Affairs, integration, European and international mobility
- Employment, education and social policies
- Rights, gender, active citizenship and Civic Service
- Culture, sport, health, environment and legality

And the two working groups:

- On prisons phenomenon
- On the monitoring and mapping of the local platforms of youth representativeness

○ FEATURES:

Is the only Italian national platform existing and it acts as recognized actors by the Italian Youth Department for consultation about youth policy.

The variety of the member' youth organizations (young political parties, youth NGO, trade union and so on) allows to support and promote different need of the young people, by acting in different policy field. It also has a national pool of trainers that join together experts in the field of participatory processes and non formal education to provide a structured support to its activities and its member organisation, if and when needed.

○ CHALLENGES:

Advocacy for youth rights e advocacy for youth organizations needs to be integrated.

Involvement and achievement of as many young people as possible and therefore their diversity and needs.

Always seek common points of convergence between member organizations and define a common position.

Have the same speed as the requests that should be answered, also using evidence-based results.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

The will of those who believed in this project from the beginning was and is to give voice to the young generations to strengthen the network of relationships between youth associations and to be promoters of their interests in the Government, the Parliament, the social and economic institutions and civil society. Putting the value of young people at the center of political debate and social initiative is the mission of this forum. Personal growth and the integration of the new generations are in fact the decisive challenges for guaranteeing social quality and democracy in our country, because there was a decline in the number of children and there weren't many leaders either, and those who stayed were not many and they were quite young. (Maria, FNG Spokesperson, Interview)

PLATFORM OF YOUTH ORGANISATION

EUROPEAN YOUTH FORUM

WWW.YOUTHFORUM.ORG

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

- To Join an European platform for youth organizations
- To know better how youth voice is heard at European level
- To support the advocacy for youth rights at EU level

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Established in 1996, as a result of the merging of three European platforms; now the European Youth Forum is an unique platform, made up of 104 National Youth Councils and International Non-Governmental Youth Organisations, which are federations of youth organisations.

WHAT THEY DO:

Mainly Advocacy activities to promote youth rights, but also related to the following topics:

Participation

Social & Economic Inclusion

Stronger Youth Organisations

Sustainable Development

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

Their governance bodies are a Board, Elected for a two year mandate made up of 11 young volunteers, and the Secretariat, made up by 25 young professionals working full-time to support the Board and the Member Organisations in their daily work. Members contribute to the platform through consultations, training/seminars, representation at external meetings.

Their working plan 2014-2018 is based on Youth Participation, Stronger Youth Organisations, Youth Autonomy and Inclusion and they plan to reach these aims through setting an Agenda on Youth Affairs, Empowered Member Organisations and a Rights-based approach in all their work

The advocacy strategy is mainly characterized by the organisation of thematic events, participation to EU meetings with related stakeholder (EU commission, Council of Europe, etc..)

The production of surveys and studies about Young European status, problems and needs

○ FEATURES:

Their vision is “To be the voice of young people in Europe” where young people are equal citizens and are encouraged and supported to achieve their fullest potential as global citizens. Role in the European Structured Dialogue process as main recognized actors in the organisation:

The recognition of a consultative status for the main EU Institutions dealing youth policy

The variety of the member organisation that are different from many points of view, involving both national youth councils and various NGOs involved and experienced in many different topics and areas

The possibility to measure and be the "thermometer" of the EU youth feelings

○ CHALLENGES:

To have a strong and effective connection with the bodies and communities of the territories they represent, also with a concrete outcome for them, strengthening the energies to reach the goals all the youth european communities are expecting for the leading youth platform in the continent.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

The biggest challenges that young people are facing is not having access to quality jobs and having a harder time becoming autonomous individuals. The future feels gloomy and the opportunities are limited. Young people are not participating in democracy in the traditional forms and there needs to be an effort from decision makers and institutions to address questions that are relevant to our generation. [...] The Youth Forum can and should advocate strongly for youth rights! We need to become stronger in our advocacy work and make sure we are achieving results. These efforts will have more impact if the youth movement behind it is strong and our voice is loud. (Johanna, Interview, F)

EUROPEAN STRUCTURED DIALOGUE

 EUROPEAN COMMISSION

EUROPEAN STRUCTURED DIALOGUE

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

[HTTPS://EC.EUROPE.EU](https://ec.europa.eu)

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Be engaged at European level about youth policy
Follow European Union's youth policy
Participate to a large European consultation

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

The Structured Dialogue is the result of the A New Impetus for European Youth (White paper, 2001) and a sequence of the European Youth Pact (2005). Those documents emphasize the importance to consult young people on policy fields that affect them directly. In 2005, a European Union Council Resolution invited the European Commission and the Member States to develop a Structured Dialogue with young people and youth organizations, experts on youth issues and public decision makers. The biggest boost for its implementation happened with the renewed framework for European cooperation in the youth field (2010-2018) adopted in 2009 through the Council Resolution that recognize young people as key actors in society that should be considered as an important resource

WHAT THEY DO:

Structured Dialogue is a means of mutual communication between young people and decision-makers in order to implement the priorities of European youth policy cooperation and to make young people's voice heard in the European policy-shaping process. It is a consultative process, implemented by the European Commission, that aims to increase cooperation with civil society and get firsthand input from young people. It is made up of one main event, the EU Youth Conference organised by the EU country currently holding the EU Presidency.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

The Structured Dialogue is linked with the cycles of the European Presidencies. Every 6 months, the presidency changes.

One Cycle of Structured Dialogue covers 3 cycles of European Presidencies of the European Union, which means in total 18 months and during 6 months of each Presidency.

The themes and topics for discussion are decided at European level by EU Youth Ministers; then a committee of the current trio of EU Presidency countries, the European Commission and the European Youth Forum is responsible for coordinating the process and deciding upon sets of questions to be asked to young people across Europe twice a year.

These questions are then used as the basis for national consultations in each EU country, which are organised by National Working Groups, and in most cases they are led by youth councils and include other youth organisations and stakeholders. Some international youth organisations also consult their members and give feedback on the questions on an ad hoc basis.

The results of the national consultations and any additional input from international youth organisations are compiled into background documents for EU Youth Conferences, where youth representatives and policy makers have the opportunity to work together and present a joint message to the EU. The EU Youth Conferences take place twice a year and are hosted by the country that holds the EU Presidency.

The Presidency country will usually promote the recommendations of its EU Youth Conference and present them to the Council of the European Union to ensure they are reflected in Council Resolutions or Conclusions adopted by EU Youth Ministers.

The conference recommendations are also used by the European Commission to inform its future policy development.

○ FEATURES:

National Youth organisations or National Youth Councils have a vital role to play in the Structured Dialogue, as they are part of the National Working Groups and they can speak on behalf of a great number of young people.

Getting involved in the Structured dialogue is a way for young people to make their voice heard, but also to contribute by giving concrete recommendation and concrete input to the Council of ministers.

The first part of the national consultation most of the time is done online with the publication of surveys to which young people can participate. National Youth Organisation and National Youth Councils often organized local events to consult young people.

○ CHALLENGES:

The process of Structured Dialogue is still not well known by youngsters that are not involved in youth organisation or political process.

The impact of this process on young people depends on the implementation of the political outcomes by the Member States through concrete measures and the involvement/commitment of youth representatives on attending and actively participating on the European discussion and on the national working group.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

The SD has been getting some visible results on the political decision on the European Level. Some results from the EU Youth Conferences organized during the last cycles were taken into consideration on the Council Resolution and others have been implemented at European Level. For example:

Provide more funds to increase the number of projects through Youth In Action Programme and Erasmus + programme;

Increase the support for all youth activities focused on intercultural dialogue and participation of young people in the EU and third countries;

Recognition of the youth work and youth organizations as a way to develop skills and competences for youth;

Establishment of the Youth Guarantee Program at European Level.

“I will take these recommendations and submit them to the Council of Youth Ministers that I will convene later this year. I also think that improving young people’s participation in Europe is a shared responsibility. All of the participants of this conference can and should add their contribution to the process. But beyond them, we also need to make participation a reality for all young people in Europe.”
(Claude Meisch, Minister of Education, Children and Youth of Luxembourg, EU Youth Conference on “empowering young people for political participation in democratic life in Europe”- 2015)

RESEARCH RECCOMANDATIONS

PERSPECTIVES OF POLICY MAKERS ON EU AND ON YOUTH ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP

Do more to support the **development of evidence-based general national social, educational and cultural policies** aimed at eradicating structural inequality amongst youth populations!

The next generation of **European Youth Policy** should take its point of departure in the significant differences between the lives and contexts of groups of young people in Europe (heterogeneity) and their relative inclusion or exclusion in opportunities for participation in civic and political life (inequalities).

Place the role of **critical political and civic education** centre stage in youth policy.

The risk of isolating youth policy to those working in the public sector should be mitigated through **partnerships with civil society organisations and networks**.

Widen and develop good practices like **Structured Dialogue and Erasmus+**

INTERNATIONAL YOUTH PANEL POSITION PAPER

RECOMMENDATION ON THE BLUE PAPER –PERSPECTIVES OF POLICY MAKERS ON EU AND ON YOUTH ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP

1

A strong and long-lasting investment aimed at European youth policy should be ensured; awareness must be risen towards more common or joint programs of all countries. A positive example in this respect is the new European Solidarity Corps. A European civil service that would enable all young people who request to spend a period of their lives in active citizenship and service to the Union with the experience in another European country. It is important that such policies are connected to and interlinked with already existing ones, aiming to guarantee sustainability and coherence over the years. Special emphasis deserves to be put on youth organizations or initiatives trying to follow a structured cross-sectoral cooperation among institutions and NGOs at all levels: local, regional, and national ones.

4

Next generation of European Youth Policy should take the **point of departure in heterogeneity and inequalities in the long run interests of all European youth groups** to get instruments and resources to become active European citizens. The Institutions should recognize, support and cooperate with youth organizations and civil society. We stand for a greater involvement from the local to the European level of young people by expanding the opportunities for participation by ensuring higher quality and sustainability of social and civic participation processes. We all must become better with reaching out to young citizens in our countries – so that we are by the same extent smarter and better organised as there are young people less organised or represented. We must encourage young people to feel in charge of their fate and we need to explain our systems and institutions much more easily.

2

Creating jobs for young people must be at the center of EU policies. Community policies must focus on fighting youth unemployment and, consequently, social exclusion. The abovementioned measures are however likely to be ineffective if they are not activated - at a community level – in form of a special plan to promote employment, especially among young people- and which is able to reverse the trend that followed the 2008 crisis. As a result, in many countries the number and quality job opportunities decreased. There is a need to provide financial incentives to encourage employers to create stable and quality job opportunities for young people, to invest in education and training of their labor force. Only through innovation the economic situation can be improved in a sustainable way. Hence, a focus on the young generation and investments into them and their education is a necessity in ensuring not just social peace but economic success of entire nations. At the same time, young people need to be protected against discriminatory employment practices and rigorous abuse.

3

As long as Structured Dialogue as well as Erasmus+ seem to work well in serving and promoting the development of a European identity, EU Institutions need to continuously **maintain, reinforce and implement all programme that ensure and stimulate the empowerment of young people, lifelong learning and non-formal education.**

ACTIVE EUROPEAN CITIZENSHIP FOR ALL

GOING BEYOND GENDER INEQUALITIES

**INVOLVING MIGRANT AND ETHNIC
MINORITIES**

TARGETING DISADVANTAGED YOUTH

**INNOVATIVE PRACTICES FOR INDIVIDUAL
SELF DEVELOPMENT**

RECCOMANDATIONS

ACTIVE EUROPEAN CITIZENSHIP FOR ALL

● COLOUR YOUTH

GOING BEYOND GENDER INEQUALITIES

COLOUR YOUTH

WWW.COLOURYOUTH.GR

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

An organisation run by and for the same target group of its activities
Supporting LGBTQ rights, starting from an advocacy group having the promotion of active citizenship
The advocacy of LGBTQ youth and the creation of a safe environment in the core of what it stands for.

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Colour Youth is an organisation created in 2011 from the the notice of the lack of a youth-oriented LGBTQ organisation and that would be exclusively run by and for LGBTQ youth.

Colour Youth was founded by young volunteers in Athens Pride. They were already active in LGBTQ issues and wanted to create a safe space for LGBTQ youth, to promote awareness of issues concerning LGBTQ youth, and advocate for LGBTQ issues. From the moment Colour Youth became a registered organisation, they started having an active presence in all aspects of civic engagement concerning LGBTQ issues, with press releases, public statements with the organisation's positions and demands.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

Social activism is in the very core of the organisation's foundation. More than specific events, the organisation is tackling the issues is working at with:

Weekly meetings open to everyone, taking place every Saturday, in the organisation's offices. They sometimes have a theme, for example there is a talk about issues and/or ideas such as LGBT history, misogyny, etc., or they are open as a safe place to meet other LGBTQ youth and 'chill out'.

Monthly meeting of groups on different issues and topics; Personal counselling sessions with a psychologist; Confidential recording of incidents of violence or discrimination based on sexual orientation or gender identity/expression.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

Colour Youth is deeply invested in following a democratic paradigm inside the organisation as well as pursuing democracy in the public sphere.

There are set rules in every meeting, in order to ensure participation and respect:

no interrupting,

respecting preferred gender pronouns,

no use of insulting language for any minorities (including psychiatric diagnoses).

○ FEATURES:

The most interesting element of Colour Youth, and the one that clearly sets it apart from many other organisations on Greece, is their attitude towards democracy, especially because it is exemplified on their own practices.

Their conceptualisation of what constitutes action is part of the organisation's legacy until today. The organisation stands for a strong public appearance; they make their presence felt in all major events of the Greek LGBTQ community, such as the Pride marches (in Athens, Thessaloniki, Crete, & Patras) as well as any other demonstrations for LGBTQ (including feminist and gender based violence) issues. Beyond the public face, another very interesting aspect of active citizenship concentrates in the creation of a community. Because the organisation's focus is a disenfranchised population, its members often having little or none support from their families and original communities, Colour Youth fills this gap by creating a community, a network of people and relationships for youth to rely upon. In its essence, this is a deeply political act, even though it isn't formally framed as such, and has a deep impact on all aspects of Colour Youth's actions. As a result, action is also conceptualized as creating community and striving for relationship.

○ CHALLENGES:

the quick succession of individuals in key positions; because of the age restrictions (maximum 30 years old), its members are mostly university students, and they often leave Greece for post-graduate studies.

to manage to combine the quick succession of persons in positions of responsibility with the retention of skills and knowledge. Every elected board has to manage and supervise a number of programs and projects through all aspects of their course:

administration, implementation, and financial stewardship. At the same time, they have to manage day-to-day activities and respond to crises.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

An active citizen is not only someone that seeks support, but also one who commits to connecting. The one that feels that in order for change to happen, and change also includes himself or herself, he or she needs to work the connection in any community that he or she belongs to. To learn, to listen, to abandon the blind shields, to ask questions, they will have to commit to a process of connecting, a process in which they will open up, and they will leave space for the others to open up. Most of the citizens that I would describe as “active”, persons or groups, are in fact isolated, and remote from this notion [of connecting]. (Interview, Elena)

INVOLVING MIGRANT AND ETHNIC MINORITIES

● MY LIFE MY SAY

INVOLVING MIGRANT AND ETHNIC MINORITIES

MY LIFE MY SAY

WWW.MYLIFEMYSAY.CO.UK

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Involving young people from excluded backgrounds
Create space for discussion political topics
Use institutional tools in order to let young people voice heard

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

My Life My Say (MSMS) is a youth-led, youth focused youth political participation organisation dedicated to bringing young people from excluded backgrounds into contact with UK politicians and to assisting them in expressing their opinions about the effects of policy. MLMS was founded in 2013 by Chief Executive Officer (CEO) Mete Coban, a local Labour party councillor who was elected in 2014 at the age of 21.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

MLMS aim at bringing young people into (institutional, parliamentary) politics by relating politics to their everyday experiences and concerns. MLMS refers to this as 'rebranding politics'.

Its work consist mainly of EU and Starbucks-funded 'Café Europe' events. Based on an idea about the Eighteenth century civic public sphere, young people would be invited by MLMS to discuss an aspect of politics and learn about the positive benefits of the EU for young people over free coffees.

Using the CEO's personal and political connections with local and national politicians, MLMS was able to establish an All Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) on a Better Brexit for Young People and to act as the group's secretariat (all APPGs are required to have an external organisation secretariat). All Party Parliamentary Groups in the UK are interest-based political support groups composed of ministers of Parliament (MPs) who come from the three major UK parties (Labour, Liberal Democrats, and Tory). The purpose of most APPGs is to advocate on behalf of an issue or interest, connecting civil society stakeholders with parliamentarians who could advocate for particular policy changes.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

The café events begin with inspirational speeches about youth citizenship from the CEO followed by discussions in groups about particular political issues and how these issues relate to and impinge on young people's lives.

As part of the APPG process, in 2017 the organisation held several roundtable public events (at Parliament, the European Commission London office, and in event venues around London) designed to inform and include young people in the process of consulting on its work to connect youth views about Brexit to decision makers.

○ FEATURES:

The presence of a consistent number of young people from black and Asian minorities is closely link to CEO inner London social and professional networks.

The participation in the APPG provides a mechanism in which particular social interest groups can be connected to powerful support within policy making structures.

The format of MLMS' youth events was almost always inclusive of opportunities for young people to perform youth active citizenship, firstly through attending the event; and through providing feedback that would inform MLMS' reporting to policymakers, or by engaging in debates about specific political issues.

○ CHALLENGES:

The organisation is much centred and the need is to expand the centers of responsibility and decisions in order to have greater sharing of organizational solutions.

Participate to institutional tables requires a high level of political literacy and institutional connectedness.

Many of the participants are personal friends recruited to either be trustees, occasional representatives or attendees at the youth events.

The geographical location of the events play a significant role in what kind of young people participate.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

'Our duty here at MLMS is to make sure we can rebrand politics and make it more accessible to young people.' (Metin Coban, Founder and CEO)

"And actually I think to be central to what's happening in terms of Brexit you need to be in London really. Because a lot of what's happening is right here. And I thought we're quite central to everything at the moment because we have APPG, and I feel like I'm most useful here." (Staff member of MLMS)

INNOVATIVE PRACTICES FOR INDIVIDUAL SELF DEVELOPMENT

● DD ACADEMY

INNOVATIVE PRACTICES FOR INDIVIDUAL SELF DEVELOPMENT

DD ACADEMY

WWW.DDAKADEEMIA.EE/EN/

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Innovative practices
Self development

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

DD Academy is a non-profit program of The Foundation for Science and Liberal Arts Domus Dorpatensis, which is a social enterprise that at least partly funds its own youth development program. The program of DD Academy is managed, shaped and created by the young people themselves. The basis for their program is strong emphasis on civic involvement of young people and the focus on learning by doing, participation, encouragement, and getting access to the networks of like minded active young people. To support young people in their goals, DD Academy provides extensive training and practical experiences in a safe environment.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

DD Academy inspires young people to direct their attention towards solving societal issues and defending open society. Their program is targeted primarily for those young people who have no previous experiences with active participation.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

They run a self-development program which brings participating youth together for 13 weekend sessions from October to June.

Besides organising the youth development program, DD Academy team organises annual youth conference called 'School of Change' and publishes a web-magazine for young people who are interested in societal issues and creating a change.

○ FEATURES:

DD Academy is led by young people and the program is managed, shaped and created by the young people for young people.

The program is targeted primarily at those young people who have no previous experiences with active civic participation; there are no strict age limits or education requirements and motivation is considered the most important requirement to participate.

The team of DD Academy do not have any doubt that young people are very much capable to be civically and politically active.

○ CHALLENGES:

Tailoring a program to fit the diverse needs of more experienced participants. The funding of labour that goes into running the program. Despite the fact that DD Academy is in a better position than most of the other youth organisations, one cannot say either that there are enough resources for long-term development of the program. The whole program functions currently on a voluntary basis and it may not be optimal solution in the long run

RESEARCH RECCOMANDATIONS

FOCUSING ON INEQUALITIES IN YOUTH ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP: FINDINGS FROM LARGE EUROPEAN SURVEYS

School curricula should involve ample **opportunities for students' learning about Europe**. This also implies that schools need to be sufficiently resourced to offer opportunities for exchange with other European countries. Schools should provide their students with opportunities to foster positive identifications with their countries. Fostering positive identification with one's country can have important psychological consequences as it is positively connected to European identity.

Individual-level inequality can be counteracted by addressing contextual inequality.

While it is unlikely that socioeconomic inequalities will cease to exist, our findings point to possibilities to counteract individual inequalities in schools and through decreasing economic and other inequalities at the country level.

Measures for reducing youth unemployment should be implemented.

Unemployment not only lowers one's individual socioeconomic status (e.g. income), which has negative effects on active European citizenship. Countries with massive youth unemployment are generally characterized by decreased opportunities for European and international level participation of young people.

Economic inequalities but also inequalities in relation to gender must be targeted.

Living in an unequal society clearly has a negative impact on youth's psychological European citizenship and their participatory practices. Thus, economic redistribution within the European Union but also policies that help to reduce gender inequality are supportive of youth active citizenship.

INTERNATIONAL YOUTH PANEL POSITION PAPER

RECOMMENDATION ON THE BLUE PAPER —FOCUSING ON INEQUALITIES IN YOUTH ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP: FINDINGS FROM LARGE EUROPEAN SURVEYS

1 The EU and Member States should develop and implement tailored mechanisms to tackle multiple levels of discriminations such as those based on age, ethnicity, sexual orientation, disability, religion, political preferences, gender identity, gender expression or socio-economic background. To reduce inequalities in the active citizenship of young people in Europe, the European Institutions should encourage **more measures to support local Institutions against social exclusion of young people**, starting from school, from active employment policies up to local support programs to young NEET.

3 **Youth and education need to play a role.** We encourage that the funding for exchange programmes, other e.g. than sports activities, has sufficient funds allocated from Erasmus Plus. We believe that every young person should have the chance for a European experience. It needs to be considered that youth exchange activities have to be for all and for instance have not a lobby as strong as e.g. sports.

5 **National Youth Councils should, as the main youth stakeholders, be empowered to take part and have a role in the implementation of inclusion policy for young people.** National Youth Councils should thus receive adequate support through the future youth programme and from national authorities to effectively fulfill this role. This could be encourage e.g. though a factor that is considering and awarding these youth councils who show active efforts in providing assistance and encouraging best practices exchange in reaching out to young citizens, that are not yet organized, so as to give more young people a voice.

7 Aiming towards active citizenship works best by not just engaging with different age groups but also by **acknowledging differences in representation of woman and men.** Especially young woman need to be taught and empowered to become active citizens and to lead. This way, we can provide better opportunities for all.

2 Active European citizenship must be encouraged with more lifelong learning programs implemented starting from elementary school. The national Institutions must encourage schools and training agencies at all stages to **promote greater opportunities for international mobility and exchange of good practices for inclusion of young people** complement the school curriculum. In order to reduce the mismatch between education systems and labor market, Member States should constantly update the curricula with a priority on practical and soft skills development. Furthermore, it is necessary that the Member States promote more training programs for teachers in relation to active European citizenship, and to promote the involvement of youth and student organizations in the definition of curricular and European exchanges between students and teachers.

4 The European Institutions and National have to monitor on the abuse of the internship that will no longer be for free but properly compensated to avoid precarious conditions and to ensure youth autonomy. It is necessary to involve youth organizations in the identification of the priorities and real needs of young people for a better and stronger implementation of the active labor market policies. The European Institutions must ensure the harmonization of the labor market in Europe, with measures dedicated to the creation of more jobs for young people, **encouraging turnover in public administration and the principle of intergenerational solidarity.**

6 **European Institutions and Member States should share more the responsibility of the inclusion of young migrants** both coming from European countries and from outside (young refugees, asylum seekers, unaccompanied minors etc favoring inclusion and employability through the exchange of good practices that aim to improve their European active citizenship and the access into the European labour market.

RAISING THE YOUTH VOICE WITHIN OLD AND NEW MEDIA

THE INSTAGRAM ENGAGED CITIZEN

“OLD AND DEAR RADIO”!

FROM ONLINE-TO-OFFLINE TO SOCIAL
MEDIA VIRALITY

RECCOMANDATIONS

THE INSTAGRAM ENGAGED CITIZEN

CONTENTS

● MY LIFE MY SAY

THE INSTAGRAM ENGAGED CITIZEN

MY LIFE MY SAY

WWW.MYLIFEMYSAY.CO.UK

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Developing way of using social media to foster youth participation

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

MLMS was founded in 2013 by Mete Coban, a local Labour party councillor who was elected in 2014 at the age of 21 with the mission to involve more marginalised young people in institutional politics in the UK by influencing national policy making to become more inclusive of youth opinions about and experiences of policy outcomes (termed by MLMS as youth voice).

WHAT THEY DO:

They communicate to young people via social media the importance and impact of giving young people access and exposure to institutional politics and political processes. They document on the major social media platform the participation of the organisation to Institutional events related to youth policy. Media platforms played a key role in MLMS' attempts to engage young people with politics and interest them in policy-making.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

MLMS both advertise opportunities to participate in, but also perform their own youth citizenship online, usually through social media platforms (especially Twitter, Instagram and Facebook). They use a mixture of inspirational videos and messages (created by others) and links to national media platforms on which they appeared, or national political celebrities with whom they appeared.

MLMS' main repertoires of media action consisted of:

Advertisement of its own events, resources, and happenings mainly on Twitter and Instagram;

The performance of status (celebrities, politicians, appearances on national media), documenting MLMS staff members' personal journeys as active citizens taking forward youth concerns;

Campaigning via announcements or reminders, retweets of other media content relevant to the campaign, and/or publicising the campaigns of others

○ FEATURES:

During the event one staff member is completely dedicated to take photo of the initiatives and instantly upload to social media the photos and the comment.

This social performances encourage the young followers to see in the members of organization an examples of youth citizenship success – in fact of empowerment – that can be emulated.

With social media platform it is possible to reach hundreds of people in few minutes.

○ CHALLENGES:

The organisation is much centred and the need is to expand the centers of responsibility and decisions in order to have greater sharing of organizational solutions.

No feedback or updating comment after the event where MLMS was present.

Number of followers of the social profile organisation (if low number no impact as desired)

Risk that the post on social media remain just appearance and lack of content or follow up in term of networking outcomes

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

So, what we do at MLMS, and how we go about doing that, it's about getting people around the table who represent different areas. I can bring that, to make me understand what that need is. At the same time, once you have like a rough idea from those discussions, and research that you conduct yourself, than what I would say to do is looking at, look at the digital element, put it out on the digital side and see if you can get young people to actually sort of like agree disagree with what you're talking about, and respond to it. Because then that will give you, as opposed to reaching like a hundred people face to face, that will give you like maybe a thousand people that you can reach. So you've got both sides. (Metecoban, Founder and CEO)

“OLD AND DEAR RADIO”

CONTENTS

● RADIOIMMAGINARIA

“OLD AND DEAR RADIO”

RADIOIMMAGINARIA

WWW.RADIOIMMAGINARIA.IT

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

A creative youth-adult organisation where adolescents and adults work together for the same objective, in which members can have a powerful role in promoting their own active civic protagonism.

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Radioimmaginaria is a youth co-led organisation, a European network with its main office located in Castel Guelfo di Bologna, a small city in the province of Bologna, Emilia-Romagna region. As a media hub and can be considered a unique case of adolescents' radio network in Italy and in Europe. “The first and only Teenage Network in Europe made up, directed and presented by teenagers between 11 and 17 years old.”

The association Radioimmaginaria Media Hub was created on March the 31st, 2012, by 7 associates. The project of a radio came after the implementation of a project about cinema in schools called Aria Immaginaria (Imaginary Air) that aimed at promoting a discussion, from adolescents' point of view, about the issue of bullying in their school.

Radioimmaginaria Media Hub is an association entirely supported by its founders, by the generosity of speakers' parents, and by foundations', associations', institutions' and privates' donations.

WHAT THEY DO:

The main office consist of a professional studio for recording, live broadcasting and meetings located in a renovated little old building (old public weighing) that was recovered. Members of RI are called Tipi Immaginari (Imaginary Fellows); they are adolescents from 11 to 17 years old who are 'partners' of the radio with the consent of their parents as they are minors. A group of 20 young people from 18 to 21 years old and 3 adults over 40 years old are also involved. Members come from almost 33 different places in Italy and 7 in the rest of Europe.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

Activities and radio broadcasts are tagged and labelled by a hashtag (#), that stands for the strong link between online language and the use of social networks. It is possible to distinguish radio broadcasts, radio projects and events. Radio broadcasts are labelled with the name of #Okkinsu (Eyes up) that is the logo of RI and stands for the eyes up facial expression that adolescents usually make when adults ask them for their future life. This name is also the shows schedule that is composed by different shows:

#14e15, a daily program, in live or registered edition, that is transmitted at h. 14:15 because it comes from the daily radio programs that spread news during that time of the day. For Radioimmaginaria, adolescents needed to have a daily program that was not so “boring” like the traditional daily news program in radio or TV. In every activity they ensure:

to promote a protected protagonism and the engagement of adolescents and children;

to support the development of their potential in the transition phase from childhood to

adolescence to emerging adulthood through a creative method;

to use the new media, including social networks critically, to produce attractive and smart content;

to improve soft skills and transversal competencies, such as relational, social and technical ones

○ FEATURES:

Adolescents and young adults of RI can be considered empowered and empowering due to their role as enactors of their own decisions and choices and to the mediating role they have for their peers. They have the opportunity to use their language (slang and informal) and to improve their skills having an active role with the initial support of adults. Broadcasts follow the language, the slang of teenagers with the aims to let them feel comfortable during the programs, to express their ideas with their words and to involve other adolescents who listen to them.

○ CHALLENGES:

Their actions try to challenge the general misrepresentation of adolescents as “slaves of a virtual world” or “passive” or “asleep” and they proposed an innovative format to create a dialogue with institutions, to tackle the lack of perspectives between them. Also the local perspective and the venue of the main office in a small city like Castel Guelfo di Bologna is a challenging set-up for a structured network with local, national and european activities

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

Sometimes, you think that our future is far away, that there is time, then, you are at the last year of high school and you say: “what do I have to do now?” and you don’t know and, then you settle for one job that you find, that is not your job and you feel it is not what you really like. Let’s say that we hope to let our peer understand that, it’s never too early to take care for our future. It’s ok to deal with since now, before arriving to the end of the school, that can be late. (Interview, 19, M)

FROM ONLINE-TO-OFFLINE TO SOCIAL MEDIA VIRALITY

CHAPTER 1

● MOMENTUM

FROM ONLINE-TO-OFFLINE TO SOCIAL MEDIA VIRALITY MOMENTUM

WWW.PEOPLESMOMENTUM.COM

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Developing alternative way of using social media and offline media in order to support a political movement/candidates

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Momentum is an incredible and almost accidental success story in active citizenship. It is a cross-generational progressive left wing activist organisation and political campaign group. Founded in September 2015 by four Labour Party activists from different backgrounds it has become one of the more effective campaigning organisation.

WHAT THEY DO:

The try to get people to the polls to vote for their favoured candidate through a mixture of online and offline activities. Some of those activities are related to traditional campaigning initiatives (Daily phone banking), others are really innovative and more youth directed (use of app, websites, social media and video platform)

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

“My Nearest Marginal,” a simple but highly innovative website aimed at encouraging members and supporters to identify the marginal seats closest to them and to volunteer or canvass there.

They are engaged in traditional daily phone banking (using their time to call and canvass labour supporters over the phone) at the national office, but also used online apps that allowed Momentum volunteers and supporters to engage in phone and text banking from their own homes. They have used also app as Tinder not for the purpose they have been created but for opening chat about politics

○ FEATURES:

Apart from the digital tools being used to mobilise offline during the campaign period discussed above, Momentum’s national office had a dedicated digital media team of 4-6 young people in their 20s and 30s, who were responsible for creating and editing a staggering amount of online content, much of which was made directly to engage young people. The digital media team respond to news in real-time and quickly develop poignant and funny ideas for videos or memes to respond. This type of instant agility and quick collaborative response is a major reason their social media engagement efforts were so successful.

○ CHALLENGES:

Good knowledge of media tools and applications

Dedicated digital media team that is responsible only for this task

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

[During] the general election, we launched a phone-calling app; phone banking before that was an incredibly exclusionary system, right? [...] So, you can only do it with people who are willing to give up a whole evening. When we launched the app, we had people calling from their own homes. We found that the people who called the most were the people that lived in the most remote regions. People who had the least access to that in the past. 'Cause it was the first time they were able to get engaged." (Munir, Momentum member)

RESEARCH RECCOMANDATIONS

PUTTING EUROPE TOGETHER: WHICH EUROPE AND WHAT YOUTH IN THE MEDIA TODAY

Enhance new forms of advocacy journalism for EU active citizenship:

use strategic communication both to provide audiences with useful multimedia tools (such as storytelling, contextualisation of data, comparison between different sources, etc.) and to give attention to the real practices and life-experiences.

Tackle the issue of the lack of a shared European news agenda by comparing different sources (including sources coming from the EU and other countries) to cover the same event/topic. **Devote more space to an articulated discussion on Europe and European issues, beyond contingencies and emergencies, also through the involvement of EU representatives and citizens.**

Face the contradiction between the old and the new informal ways to engage themselves in the public issues of democracy: representative, deliberative, participative are the different qualifications of the same view of citizens consultation; may be, the future of democracy has to tackle new challenges coming from technology, distrust, new forms of authoritarianism, but also from new ways of social relations and practices, that youth could reveal.

Rather than basing the coverage of European issues and events only on institutional sources, it could be more fruitful to **promote debate opening to the controversies and issues that are central in the European citizens'** (and especially young people's) everyday lives. For example, the news coverage could be enriched (also through the involvement of younger generations of journalists) by combining local and global perspectives, as a way to abandon the traditional constraints imposed by the political discourse.

Devote more resources on "indirect information" coming from **fiction, television products, and youth-oriented media entertainment** with the goal of building a new mutual trust between young audiences and the traditional media: for example promoting comparative analysis among the Erasmus+ university students about their consumption of different national and international web/TV products.

INTERNATIONAL YOUTH PANEL POSITION PAPER

RECOMMENDATION ON THE BLUE PAPER – PUTTING EUROPE TOGETHER: WHICH EUROPE AND WHAT YOUTH IN THE MEDIA TODAY

1 European Institutions could share more their work and agenda by new Media like Twitter, Facebook and others. Moreover, they should **create a forum were the citizen could discuss and present suggestions about various EU policies.**

2 In order to avoid the democratic deficit, which is aggravated by the national media reporting the EU news from the national point of view, thus increasing the strengths and weaknesses of each country, the European Institutions should **have a EU programme in any European television palimpsest to communicate and inform citizens, specially youth, about measures and opportunities.**

3 The European Institutions could include and give **more visibility to work of political representatives of all member countries**, in order to reduce the perception of “democratic deficit” and decrease the news where EU appears like an abstract entity. It is essential that all democratically elected political parties within the European Institutions ensure greater communication and dissemination of the policy agenda with their national parties.

4 Whereas it will be young people to decide the future, we should enable them to think about all the situations that may involve their future and **not limit youth to issues related to youth unemployment and education.** The process of involvement young people, such as the “structured dialogue” should be further promoted through the European and national media, on social media and television campaigns dedicated both to the opportunity for dialogue that the results produced.

5 Taking into account that the EU is made up of countries with different economies and different social vulnerabilities, **the strategies for improving living conditions, greater involvement and approach of young people as European citizens should be adapted to every country.** The positive image of young people and their capacity to be entrepreneurs must be stimulated through direct dialogue and recognition of the European Institutions.

FORMAL AND NON FORMAL EDUCATIONAL CONTEXT

**ENHANCING THE “DECISION MAKING”
PROCESS AT SCHOOL**

**CONSTRUCTING AN EUROPEAN
CITIZENSHIP AT SCHOOL**

SUPPORTING THE RIGHT TO EDUCATION

**NON FORMAL EDUCATION, KEY FOR
SUCCESS**

RECCOMANDATIONS

ENHANCING THE “DECISION MAKING” PROCESS AT SCHOOL

● **PRENDIPARTE**

ENHANCING THE “DECISION MAKING” PROCESS AT SCHOOL

PRENDIPARTE

WWW.FACEBOOK.COM/PRENDIPARTE

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

a youth-led organisation created by high school students from the same school and who shared similar experiences of school engagement aimed to create projects to enhance youth active citizenship

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

It was created by a group of high school students from the same school and who shared similar experiences of school engagement.

The initial aim of the organisation was to create projects to enhance youth active citizenship, learning from their previous experiences within a big Italian organisation named “Libera” (Free) that deals with anti - mafia and chose legality as one of its main issues. Their links with Acmos, a national youth organisation that coordinates a national network called WeCare, allowed PrendiParte to become part of this network that provides the most important issues for discussion and trainings for their activities. The name of the organisation is strictly linked to the territory because it takes the name from one of the Bologna towers (the tower owned in the medieval times to the noble family PrendiParte; literally it means “to participate”, “to take part”), and it expresses the overarching aim of the organisation.

WHAT THEY DO:

The activities of PrendiParte are conducted both in schools and outside the school context and are often implemented by the organisation like an ongoing project based on the use of non-formal education methods and on the principles of informality and continuity (Scu.Ter. Project. - School and Territory) with organised discussions on important social issues; a project based on providing support to children and adolescents in doing their homework as an opportunity to spread basic values on active citizenship in an informal way within an institutional context Oltrescuola (After school activities); A project named Meridiano d’Europa (Meridian of Europe), referred to the line from Utoya to Lampedusa, two small islands located in opposite parts of Europe (one in the deep North of Europe and the other one in the extreme south) which have an important symbolic value respectively for youth and migrants’ history. They also organize activities outside the school context like the “P.A.Z. - Progetto Accoglienza Zaccarelli” to support the activities of a reception centre for migrants and refugees.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

Members of PrendiParte consider the organisation as an informal place to express their views, share interests and opinions with other members and with young people they meet during their activities. In fact, they act as bridging agents, constructing weak ties between young people and Institutions. As the former president of the organisation explains, they see themselves in an intermediate position between adolescents and adults.

This “mediating” position between adolescents and adults allows them to reflect continuously on their activities and to be critical on the issues that they present in schools.

PrendiParte members can be considered promoters of critical thinking: their primary intervention strategy involves organising debates about social or political issues. Thanks to their personal experience, they act as tutors for adolescents, taking care of their social and political development.

○ FEATURES:

One of the main aspects PrendiParte is based on the political positioning of their activities. The political position can be intended as actions that can influence the common good. Given that the organisation does not belong to a political party, its political vision is conceived as the opportunity to debate political issues from different perspectives allowing, within its members, youth who declare themselves to follow opposing political ideologies. The opportunity to be aware of the political aim of the organisation seems to be important for the development of the activities and projects but also for the future life of the organisation itself. The belonging to an organisation seems to have an exclusive role to bring a political message to youth: This position is strengthened by the political values that are transmitted through the activities to the youth raising critical awareness on different topics.

○ CHALLENGES:

They do not have a main office for conducting their activities but they have the opportunity to use spaces shared with other local organisations or movements. The general management of the relations between younger and older pairs it can ensure wide space to debate and deepening specific questions, but also for these motivation is not always possible to take position on it. The main challenge anyway is represented by the difficult coexistence in the network of the innovative/non-formal education activities and the use of traditional methods perceived as too formal and conventional.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

In the beginning, I threw a little stone, then obviously, thanks to the engagement of the founders, we enlarged the organisation inviting friends. ... I think that each project has some people who are role models toward young people, and they, on their turn, become role models toward their friends and people they meet; concrete example is fundamental, informing and discussing is important, but it is not sufficient, you also need action, and often it is action that is effective in changing the attitudes of other people. [...] This is important: we are attempting to deconstruct certain mental schemes of young people. Obviously, you can do it using words, but it is especially concrete behavior that works, not the behavior of an abstract person but of a concrete person that is informed, engages with them spending a lot of his/her time with them, shows that he/she wants to know them... this is what we are attempting to do, build a relationship with young people, getting to know them really. (Interview, 24, M)

CONSTRUCTING AN EUROPEAN CITIZENSHIP AT SCHOOL

● **ASSOCIAZIONE GIOVANI
IN EUROPA (AGE)**

CONSTRUCTING AN EUROPEAN CITIZENSHIP AT SCHOOL

ASSOCIAZIONE GIOVANI IN EUROPA (AGE)

WWW.AGEUROPA.EU

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

A Youth-led multicultural organisation promoting active citizenship, non-formal education and socialisation for young people inside and outside the school context

GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

AGE (Association of European Youth) is a youth led association located in Reggio Emilia (Emilia Romagna Region, North Italy), founded firstly in 2001 as a committee with the main aim to promote dialogue between citizens and European institutions to enhance critical thinking about sense of belonging to European culture and the meaning of (European) Union. (Organisation document about the history of the association, AGE archive). In 2012 a group of youth had formal re-constituted the association, the aim was explicitly connected with the specific mission of spreading civic education and promoting active citizenship among young people, which was perceived as insufficiently covered by the school curriculum. They wrote a manifesto of values that explain the reasons of the reconstitution of the organisation - using an innovative tool such as the open space technology (OST) – and its main aim, that is to educate youth for active citizenship outside the school. The process of creation of the organisation and the tools used to create projects and activities exemplify the representation of youth focused on youth ideas, capabilities and power. In fact, the association itself was established as a result of the opportunity to generate and share new ideas through the use of the Open Space Technology. This participatory methodology is considered one of the most important strategies of the organisation to promote youth volunteerism and to recruit members.

WHAT THEY DO:

Non-formal education and socialization with the aim to promote civic and social values in school and community contexts (such as youth centres) and to strengthen networking among youth at local level. The main projects are Du iu spik english (the name means “do you speak English” but it is written how it is pronounced) and Mercatino del libro. Du iu spik english project aims to improve participants’ English language skills and to recruit new members. Mercatino del libro (second hand school books market) project is based on the organisation, implementation and maintenance of a book market.

Promotion of Active citizenship. Projects aimed to promote active citizenship attempt to develop and strengthen youth’s sense of European citizenship and the idea of European Union, to foster social cohesion and cooperation at local level and between different cultures and people and to create a dialogue with European Institutions. The main projects are Ovunque, Troviamoci, Bilanci partecipativi. Ovunque (Everywhere) project is based on youth mobility in Europe. Its main objective is to promote European mobility programs for local youth; a second aim is to recruit new members. Troviamoci (Let’s meet) project is based on the collection of data about local youth organisations to promote networking, communication and cooperation among them. Bilanci partecipativi (Participatory budgets) is a project that has been recently created with the aim to meet and discuss with local politicians and government about youth involvement in the political arena.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

AGE uses different tools to spread active citizenship. The first level encompasses communication and socialisation, between members, of roles and other important information. For example, a privileged tool is the online platform where drafts of past, present and future projects are stored. This platform contains the documents describing their various projects. These include the following: a title, the name of the member of AGE who is responsible for the project's implementation, the main theme and objective, the beneficiaries, the human resources needed, the type of internal and external communication expected, a brief description of the project and a timetable. They use also an online calendar for meetings and assemblies, shared among members. Another important document is the vademecum describing the roles of members in the organisation. The vademecum illustrates step by step what every member must do in relation to the role played in the organisation as well as the rules and procedures, such as the general assembly, the board and communication procedures between members.

○ FEATURES:

The process of developing projects within AGE organisation follows specific rules. All members of AGE can propose projects and activities but they must follow a specific procedure:

1. each member of the organisation who has a new idea can propose it and develop a project;
2. ideas and projects are firstly presented to a general assembly (or even through an online group);
3. proponents of the projects then have a meeting with the president (or another member of the board) who provides support in structuring and organising the project;
4. if projects are finally approved by the board, the initiator becomes the person on charge of its organisation and implementation, with the support of a group of volunteer members, who may take the responsibility of some activities (i.e. communication activities, networking, etc.).

○ CHALLENGES:

The organisation does not have a main office, and this affects the efficiency of their work, it is a multicultural association with members of different origins and the focus of AGE as an organisation moves straight from the local to the European level, without a focus on the national level.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

Citizenship education should have continuity, year after year; instead we realised that in the school citizenship education was conducted episodically and based on the good will of some teachers, or it was conducted in part, in the sense that the only topic that was dealt was Constitution, unfortunately this is insufficient, it is important to teach also democracy, the importance of politics, because this is the ground where power is allocated. Then, attempt to understand that the problems affecting quality of life of people are related to politics and management of power (Interview, 65, M)

SUPPORT THE RIGHT TO EDUCATION

● **ARBEITERKIND**

SUPPORT THE RIGHT TO EDUCATION

ARBEITERKIND

WWW.ARBEITERKIND.DE

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

Raise awareness about social injustice connected to educational inequality
Encourage your peers through your personal example

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

ArbeiterKind was founded in 2006 and is a rather large (6000 members) association in Germany.

It has frequently been discussed in the media in recent years. Among others factors, this can be explained by partners and members who raised awareness about ArbeiterKind and showed the necessity to get active in that subject.

WHAT THEY DO:

○ ArbeiterKind operates on the national, regional and local level. Most of the volunteer staff are themselves first generation academic (with families who traditionally did not go into higher education), and report from their own experiences about their educational development.

They support pupils who aim to study at university and are, in this respect, educational pioneers in their family, meaning that their parents have no academic background. ArbeiterKind offers them contacts to other older students who were in the same situation. Besides mentoring, ArbeiterKind gets in touch with schools and offers information for pupils.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

They organize Regular's table, a common tradition in Germany. Groups with a mutual interest but also friends, meet regularly (e.g. once a week, once a month) at for example a pub or café. Regulars' table are diverse, some are structured and more obligatory; others don't work on a subject and take the regulars' table as an occasion to meet friends regularly. The content of regular tables is very different and is depending on the group, for example some meet to discuss political subjects, or exchange certain information and others just meet their friends.

They invite youth to meet them and talk about e.g. challenges or structural help in e.g. applying for scholarships.

They organise career starter event with the objective of informing young people on career options in their education. Keynote speakers and workshop leaders are invited in collaboration with the national structure.

○ FEATURES:

Most of the volunteer staff are themselves first generation academic and report from their own experiences about the educational development

Friendship play an important role in the group and it was for some the initial reason to get in touch with the organisation.

The group got resources (materials and know how) from their headquarters, too, in cases they require them.

○ CHALLENGES:

There are no reflections over political protest or other forms of active citizenship other than informing and helping other young people from socially disadvantaged backgrounds with information and knowledge.

There are no interactions on a regional level between the ArbeiterKind groups.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

In general, I would say to do the things that you do the best way you can, at your own discretion.

That how I personally would define success. (Interview to one member)

The topic itself really motivates me. Because we simply **STILL** assume that you have education if you are smart, if you are diligent, if you make an effort. [...] So that's been the case for a long time that we just have inequalities and that we are also **ESPECIALLY** in international comparison one of the countries with the lowest permeabilities, with the highest selections. [...] So the topic is somehow mine, I think it's very important and of course that has something to do with my own origin. (Interview to one member)

NON FORMAL EDUCATION, A KEY FOR SELF DEVELOPMENT

● AWESOME PEOPLE

NON FORMAL EDUCATION, A KEY FOR SELF DEVELOPMENT

AWESOME PEOPLE

WWW.AWESOMEPEOPLE.SE

YOU ARE INTERESTED IN:

New educational methods in working with youth
Spread your organization activities to an European dimension
Support self development of young people

○ GENESIS OF THE EXPERIENCE:

Awesome People was founded in 2013 in one of Sweden's smallest municipalities by a couple who had worked with young, vulnerable young people for several years. It was their experience that a lot of young people lacked the basic skills requested by the employers. This made them think about how they could help these young people which later resulted in a new method – today called PiFbase, aiming to strengthen their self-esteem. They hence decided to start the organisation to make them able to request money from both public and private foundations.

It is an organisation which works on one of the major challenges for the civil society in Sweden: to involve and encourage young people who do not usually participate or engage in their society.

○ WHAT THEY DO:

They organize different activities such as training course for youth workers about coaching, youth exchanges, inspiration labs – involving presentations and workshops with members who had been on exchanges or training courses, preparation meetings – involving planning and information about upcoming events and study visits from umbrella organisations.

○ HOW THEY DO IT:

The organisation is working with non formal education methods which can be described as self-directed learning and learning by doing. Instead of a formal lesson the young people got to for example experience, test different strategies and play in order to learn their own basis. A central theme is to actively engage the participants in the task and let them think and reflect by themselves in order to make them find the answers by themselves. The method can be described as handing over the power to the individual and let her/him find their own way to solve an issue or a problem, to let them test their capacity.

The method could also involve playing games, creating or expressing yourselves as well as coming up with, presenting and performing your own ideas, storytelling instead of formal lecturing in order to illustrate certain points.

○ FEATURES:

They fund the activities mainly with Erasmus+ programme, giving an European dimension to their local activities.

Media – both social media and mainstream public media such as newspapers and radio programmes play an important role in the organisation's work to find partners, sponsors and of course to recruit new members and participants.

Young people are both involved in the conduction of these activities as well as being the target group.

Small size of the organisation and small size member base generates preconditions for direct democracy, where the members are able to directly influence the work and reach consensus.

Personal contacts and networks are crucial for the organisation's growth and make possible to co-organise activities with the municipality.

○ CHALLENGES:

They are not able to get national funding because of the small size of the organization (in Sweden the funding system take more into account the number of members, so the size of the organizations).

The small personal resources limit the ability to distribute the work and to establish formal procedures and structures. In turn it makes the work reliant on the members' ability to combine their formal occupation – job or studies, with the work of the organisation.

○ SOME INSIGHTS.....

In Awesome People we have a vision, that vision is a generation of young people who takes initiatives to make a better world for themselves, for others and for the planet. We believe we can reach that vision if we work with our mission which is to make people be and feel awesome. When you feel awesome you have the capacity to make other people feel awesome and that is the kind of world we want, the world we strive for, where people not only thinking of themselves but also care for others. (Interview)

We are a new organisations that's only growing and growing because we are fresh, we are new thinking but we are still experienced and we are very targeted on our goals and has a completely different way of thinking, we don't think "we have always done this, this has worked before, why isn't it working now?", we think "how do we get it to work now?" so that's what I would say is the most important thing that we do and we are a role model internationally about how youth projects should work and also as a source of inspiration for a lot of others who wants to start something small that even if you're a really small group and have very little capacity you can still, you can still do very big things. (Interview)

RESEARCH RECCOMANDATIONS

UNDERSTINANDING THE ROLE OF SCHOOL EDUCATION IN PROMOTING ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP

Citizenship and political education should be systematically considered in all curricula in schools across Europe, integrating activities linked to real-life experiences.

Educational European institutions should provide **training plans and refresher courses dedicated to citizenship and European issues** for all teachers.

European and National institutions should promote greater **opportunities for cooperation and interaction between schools and youth NGOs**, in order to enhance European citizenship and civic and political involvement.

More **real, hands-on experiences linked with national and European politics** should be created, so that students can better understand political mechanisms and institutions. The organisation of **tours, visits and political debates**, as forms of promoting the meaningful acquisition of political knowledge and raising civic-minded youngsters, are recommended.

Schools should promote decision-making regarding school governance and resources for student councils and youth student organisations, **providing all students the opportunity to selfmanage activities in- and out-of-school and to co-organise activities** based on concrete bottom-up experiences.

The **use of innovative pedagogical methods** (technological ones included) is recommended, hand-in-hand with the traditional teaching materials (the textbooks), supporting **debate and critical reflection** about current political/civic issues.

Educational European institutions should further promote **training and job-shadowing opportunities** offered by the European programs (Erasmus + Adult Education), and schools should have human resources dedicated to designing and managing projects.

The gap between the school and the real life should be addressed through non-formal activities organised by the youngsters, including **opportunities for dialogue between young people and political parties** grounded on concrete experiences and consequences.

In order to **change the common downplaying of Citizenship/Political Education** (be it a subject or a transversal curricular dimension) compared to other school subjects, it is necessary to have experts in the area of citizenship and political education to collaboratively work with all teachers.

Teachers should be encouraged to engage with political issues – not assuming the educational project as an ideological project leads to depolitization, with consequences for youth citizenship.

The **creation of structured co-curricular spaces for political debate**, in which politicians could also be invited by the young people, increasing the regularity of their presence in schools.

To promote opportunities for civic and political engagement, **supporting the youngsters who want to become active but do not know how to do it** (through the provision of information and tools to the youth associations), democratising participatory resources.

To encourage **the use of alternative assessment instruments in schools**, not only focused in the exams but involving students in the decision-making processes – the school should be, first and foremost, a place of learning and not a place of assessment. The dichotomy 'assessment vs participation' should be challenged.

INTERNATIONAL YOUTH PANEL POSITION PAPER

RECOMMENDATION ON THE WORK PACKAGE 6 – REPRESENTATION OF THE EU AND YOUTH ACTIVE EU CITIZENSHIP IN EDUCATIONAL CONTEXTS

1 The “European Civic Education” should be established as a compulsory subject in all curricula in schools across Europe. More activities in schools that encourage the acquisition of new and transversal skills for life (soft skills), complementary for an active citizenship should be introduced in the direction of a restructuring of curricular programs.

2 Educational European Institutions should provide training plans and refresher courses dedicated to European issues for all career teachers. Public competitions and selections for teachers should focus more in exams and tests on European matters.

3 European and National Institutions should promote greater opportunities for cooperation and interaction between schools and youth NGOs in order to enhance European citizenship through the opportunities offered by EU for young people.

4 For a better understanding of students on how European politics and mechanisms work, there need to be more time and more hands-on experience. While teachers embrace sight visits and tours as well as discussion with politicians, the general knowledge on fundamental policy making remains too little and very vague. Here we recommend an encouragement of political debates and pointing out of opportunities in the policy making sphere.

5 Schools should provide more space for decision-making regarding school governance and resources for student councils and youth student organizations, allowing them to self-manage activities in-and-out the school.

6 While we encourage the use of up-to-date technologies and methods and encourage them in teaching, we nonetheless acknowledge the desire of students for reliable sources (such as books etc.) in the early stages of forming opinions. Good methods cannot replace all knowledge.

7 Within the curricular programs in schools should be guaranteed more activities based on concrete bottom up experiences co-organized with the students themselves and promoted through nonformal educational methodologies.

8 Educational European Institutions should further promote training and job-shadowing opportunities between teachers offered by the European programs (Erasmus + Adult Education). Each school should have office and human resources dedicated to designing and managing projects for teachers and students.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

At the end of our intense journey in making you discover some good practices of youth active citizenship in each of the eight countries involved in the Horizon 2020 project "Catch EyoU", we want to conclude with considerations and recommendations that we intend to make known to all the stakeholders involved in the definition of practices and policies in favor of young people.

In order to be able to further review the contents of the Toolkit it is necessary to state that all the initiatives described have been merged by some keys criteria for assessing active citizenship initiatives used by the researchers. The first concerns the values that the initiatives place at its core such as economic equity, social and political justice, civil and human rights. The second criteria concerns the organizational sphere which is committed to democratic principles and the organisational structure and practices also attempt to be horizontal/democratic. The last aspect concerns the possible replicability for which the initiative is sustainable over time both in terms of active and diverse youth engagement as in terms of funding models.

One of the other fundamental aspects of this analysis concerned the European dimension that some activities have shown as central and others less. With this in mind, it should be noted that, where community instruments and programmes known as the European Structured Dialogue or Erasmus + are present, greater involvement is encouraged. This facilitates the implementation of sustainable and interconnected activities as well as ensuring a more defined framework in relation to methods and definition such as networking or youth work.

From the data emerged in this Toolkit, all the activities carried out by youth organizations have as general objective to encourage the engagement of young people in society at all levels (local, national and international). Different practices for different dimensions of participation, different practices for different tools of involvement, different motivations for different groups of young people involved. These considerations lead us to affirm how it turns out to be varied and extremely challenging to involve young people, organize them and make them protagonists in society. The categories of the Toolkit represent only some issues on which it is considered important and crucial the involvement of young people, from dialogue with institutions and political decision-makers, to the inclusion of the heterogeneity of memberships in social groups or needs, concluding with the use of old and new media tools to encourage participation and representation in the media of youth issues. A specific discussion, instead, concerns the formal and non-formal educational context, in which the experiences told show how it is possible to reach high levels of involvement and elements of cross-sectorial integration between training methods and objectives.

The individual dimension of the youth participant, founder, animator or leader of youth organization has a common denominator: the absence of a lasting strong vertical connotation (although a clear division of roles and an issue concerning the replacement of the leadership) and the persistence of limits and opportunities that the voluntary/professional structure of the organization or the context in which it operates can determine.

Even though the collective dimension of organization towards the public or the community to which it is addressed is different, many of the organizations show that they have clear objectives to be achieved and tools (internal and external to the organization) to be used. For this reason and without doubts, it is possible to affirm that youth organizations can represent an organizational model that brings good social changes/practices but also professional ones for those who attend them or determine their activities.

In conclusion, encouraging the formation, support and reinforcement of the organizational processes of young people is certainly the basis for limiting disengagement and apathy; ensuring a good quality of work and the sustainability of the activities becomes fundamental in terms of reaching an active citizenship of young people. Youth organizations can not be left to perform this function, for this reason is crucial the role of European, national and local institutions that must have to ensure proactive cohabitation taking into account all the needs and diversity of its young citizens. This is the basis for a equal society in which the self becomes us and the individual becomes a community.

There is still a long way to go, but it is in the commitment to pursue these results that the freedom of our democracies is fulfilled.

Lorenzo Floresta
Project Coordinator of the International Youth Panel

BIBLIOGRAPHY

The content of this Toolkit has been extracted from the Deliverable 8.2 of the project “Catch EyoU” titled “Contexts, meanings and successful practices of young people’s participation: a cross-national report”, coordinated by Shakuntala Banaji from London School of Economics and Political Sciences and carried on by the partners of the project.

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Eva Majewski, Domniki G. Kouitzoglou, Sara Fabiana Lopes and Kuldar Adel as experts of the International Youth Panel who have been working on the Position Papers.